

Table 1. Sensitivity of MAb-ELISA in the detection of Xoo. ^a

Technique	Sensitivity at given strain concentration (cells/ml)						
	10 ⁶	10 ⁵	10 ⁴	10 ³	10 ²	10 ¹	PBS(check)
DAS-ELISA	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
DAS-ABC-ELISA	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
ID-ELISA	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
ID-ABC-ELISA	+	+	+	+	-	-	-

^a + = positive = no. OD₅₅₀ is twice that of check. - = negative.

Table 2. Specificity of MAb-ELISA in the detection of Xoo.

Technique	Specificity							
	Xoo	<i>X.o. pv. oryzicola</i>	<i>X.c. pv. malvacearum</i>	<i>X.c. pv. campestris</i>	<i>E. carotovora</i> subsp. <i>carotovora</i>	<i>P. solana-cearum</i>	<i>C. sepedonicum</i>	<i>A. tumefaciens</i>
DAS-ELISA	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DAS-ABC-ELISA	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ID-ELISA	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ID-ABC-ELISA	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

The cultures of Xoo were diluted into different concentrations (cells/ml) and tested using four methods. The sensitiv-

ity of ABC-MAb-ELISA was higher than that of ELISA; ID-ABC-ELISA had the highest (Table 1). In our experi-

ments, the sensitivity of ID-ELISA was higher than that of DAS-ELISA.

We detected some important plant pathogenic bacteria belonging to different genera or species. Negative reactions were observed on *Elwinia carotovoru* subsp. *carotovora*, *Pseudomonas solanacearum*, *Corynebacterium sepedonicum*, and *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*. We also observed negative reactions on the same species but of different pathogenic types: *X. campestris* pv. *campestris*, *X. campestris* pv. *malvacearum*, and *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzicola* (Table 2).

Our experiment showed that by adding the biotin-avidin system to the ELISA, the sensitivity of reaction could be improved without changing specificity. ABC-MAb-ELISA will be useful in detecting Xoo. □

Distribution of sheath rot (ShR) in six agroclimatic zones of Assam, India

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ShR was confined to the rice-growing areas of Cachar district in Assam during the early 1980s, but it has gradually spread to other regions. We surveyed 17 rice-growing districts representing the state's six agroclimatic zones to better understand the current status of the disease. Fields planted to different cultivars of transplanted rice located along the national highways were inspected at booting stage during the 1989 and 1990 wet seasons (Jul-Oct). We assessed all the hills in a 1-m² area at each site. ShR incidence was calculated as number of infected tillers divided by total tillers × 100.

The highest incidences of ShR were in Karimganj and Cachar districts of the Barak Valley zone (see table). Lowest incidences (4%) were in the two districts of the hill zone. No zone, however, was disease-free. Jaya and IR20 had higher infection incidence than other commonly cultivated rice. □

Sheath rot incidence in 6 agroclimatic zones of Assam, India, 1989-90.

Agroclimatic zone	District	Fields surveyed (no.)	Range of incidence (%)	Agroclimatic zone	District	Fields surveyed (no.)	Range of incidence (%)
Upper Brahmaputra Valley	Dibrugarh	4	21-30	Hill zone	Karbi Anglong	4	<5
	Sibsagar	3	11-20		North Cachar	3	<5
	Jorhat	4	31-40	North Bank Plain	Lakhimpur	3	31-40
	Golaghat	2	11-20		Sonitpur	2	11-20
Central Brahmaputra Valley	Nowgong	2	11-20	Darag	41-10		
	Marigaon	2	11-20	Barak Valley	Karimganj	4	>50
Lower Brahmaputra Valley	Kamrup	3	11-20		Cachar	3	41-50
	Borpeta	2	1-10		Total	52	
	Kokrajhar	4	11-20				
	Goalpara	3	1-10				

Chemical control of neck blast (BI) through granular fungicides

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BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. is a serious constraint to the production of scented rice in Haryana. We evaluated granular fungicides pyroquilon, chlobenthiazone, and IBP and a soil application of a recommended spray fungicide (edifenphos). Susceptible

cultivar Pakistani Basmati was transplanted in Jul 1986. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with 5- × 3-m² plots. Each treatment was replicated three times.

Fungicides were broadcast at disease initiation prior to panicle initiation. We applied pyroquilon, chlobenthiazone, and IBP at 30 and 40 kg/ha and edifenphos at 5 liters of the formulated product in 60 kg sand/ha. Disease incidence was recorded as the percent infected panicles in 250 randomly selected tillers/plot 20 d after the last application of fungicide.